

MENTAL STRESS USING HEART RATE VARIABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Mental stress is a condition that no one wants to be in. Stress can lead to a variety of issues, including depression, heart attacks, and strokes. Psychophysiological conditions can be used to describe a person's mental state of stress. The advancement of mobile device technology, as well as the sensors that go with it, can be used to assess the psychophysiological state of its users. A smartphone or smartwatch can be used to measure heart rate from a photoplethysmography signal. One of the most researched methods for assessing mental stress is heart rate variability. Our goal is to examine the subjects' stress levels while performing smartphone tasks. In this study, 41 students participated as respondents. While performing the n-back tasks, their heart rates were recorded using a smartphone. One of the performance tasks used to assess working memory and working memory capacity is the n-back task. The n-back task was also used as a stressor in this study. To determine stress levels, the heart rate dataset and n-back task results are processed and analysed using

machine learning. When compared to three other algorithms (neural network, discriminant analysis, and naïve Bayes), the k-nearest neighbour algorithm is best suited for time and frequency domain analysis classification.

Keywords: Heart Rate Variability; Mental Stress; Stress Detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of the negative effects on daily routines, many people have investigated mental stress in various fields. Mental stress can appear as a variety of symptoms and signs, ranging from physiological to psychological and behavioural manifestations. Castaldo investigated mental stress in humans using a variety of cognitive stressors in the laboratory or in real-life scenarios [1]. Some physiological signals, such as galvanic skin response, blood pressure, electroencephalogram, respiration rate, and electrocardiogram, can be used to detect stress [1]. However, one of the most researched methods for assessing mental stress is Heart Rate Variability (HRV). The variation in the interval between successive peaks of heartbeat waves is referred to as HRV. HRV is

far more sensitive in measuring stress than simply measuring heart rate. HRV analysis is a widely used noninvasive tool for assessing the autonomic nervous system (ANS) [2]. HRV analysis and use are becoming more popular due to its sensitivity to both physiological and psychological changes [3].

HRV can be studied in the time, frequency, and nonlinear domains. HRV analysis can be performed on a nominal 24-hour record (long-term HRV analysis), a 5-minute record (short-term HRV analysis), or shorter records [2]. Short-term HRV analysis allows for continuous and real-time monitoring of individual stress levels. This analysis is critical in a variety of situations or occupations, such as that of a surgeon or a driver. An ultra-short-term HRV analysis is one that is performed on HRV in less than 5 minutes in this paper.

Currently, researchers are conducting research on real-life stress detection using short-term HRV analysis. The evolution of the mobile device has been rapid over the last decade. With the proliferation of smartphones and smartwatches, the demand for short-term HRV analysis to monitor people's health and well-being is growing [4]. Some smartphones include a heart rate sensor, which provides an estimate of the average heart rate.

Rate calculated from pulse signals recorded at the fingertips. They rely on photoplethysmography (PPG). PPG illuminates

the skin with a light source and measures the intensity of the reflected light with a photodetector. Every heartbeat, pulsatile changes in reflected light cause HR estimates in reflected light to fluctuate.

Several studies on this topic had been conducted in this context. For example, using HRV in the time and frequency domains on healthy and unhealthy subjects resulted in the classification of tachycardia and bradycardia values [5]. Using statistical analysis of HRV in the time and frequency domains, Apple Watch can detect participants' relaxed and mentally stressed states [6]. Machine learning is used on ultra-short HRV features to identify a person's state of rest and stress [7]. The use of a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN) in a single pulse PPG can differentiate between valence and arousal states in a person [8].

The goal of this study is to compare mental stress detection on PPG signals obtained from smartphones using four machine learning methods. The n-back task is used as both a stressor and a performance measurement to validate the HRV measurement results. The first stage involves pre-processing PPG signals, followed by feature extraction, and finally, four machine learning methods are implemented.

2. METHODS

This study enlisted the help of 41 students who volunteered to take part. The

number of respondents is deemed adequate, as has been done in other similar studies involving between 12 and 42 respondents [6–11].

All of the participants are in good health and have written down their agreement before taking part. Participants were asked not to consume energy drinks, alcohol, coffee, or cigarettes prior to data collection and to assume they had gotten enough sleep. Before beginning the assignment, participants are given information about the purpose of data retrieval as well as instructions on the tasks they will complete. Participants will work on the n-back task while their heart rates are recorded using the smartphone's PPG sensor.

The n-back task is a continuous performance task that is commonly used in cognitive neuroscience as an assessment to measure a component of working memory and working memory capacity [12]. The subject is shown a series of stimuli, and the task is to indicate when the current stimulus matches one from n steps earlier in the sequence. The stimulant can be anything, such as pictures, colours, or the alphabet. Figure 1 depicts the stimuli used in this study in alphabetical order. The load factor n can be changed to make the task easier or harder.

Figure 1 depicts the n-back tasks.

During the data collection process, participants should sit as comfortably as possible while holding a smartphone and placing their index finger on the smartphone's heart rate sensor. They must be quiet in order to reduce body movements, particularly those of the hand while holding the smartphone, in order to avoid low signal readings. The experimental procedure is depicted in Figure 2. The experimental protocol included three test sessions, each with three n-back task stages. Participants rested for one minute at the start, end, and between each session, but their fingers remained on the heart rate sensor to measure resting conditions.

Figure 2: Procedure for Experimentation

The obtained heart rate measurement results will be pre-processed before being analysed based on the HRV features. HRV parameters are classified into time and frequency domains. Because they are calculated differently, the gaps are also addressed differently. The HRV parameters will be derived from R-R intervals using time-domain analysis. We proposed eight time domain parameters: mHR, RR, SDHR, SDRR, CVRR, RMSSD, pRR20, and pRR50. Four frequency

domain parameters were proposed: ultra-low frequency (ULF), very low frequency (VLF), low frequency (LF), and high frequency (HF) (HF). Table 1 describes the time and frequency domain HRV features.

The smartphone device used in this study is the Samsung Galaxy Note 5 with Android 7.0. (Nougat). The smartphone is powered by an Exynos 7420 processor, has 4GB of RAM, 32GB of internal storage, and a heart rate (PPG) sensor. The smartphone's PPG (photoplethysmogram) sensor is validated using two commercial heart rate measuring devices in the form of a chest belt, the Garmin HRM3-SS and the Magene Mover 2. The Pearson correlation test results for the two devices are 0.9884 and 0.9355. Values close to one indicate a very strong relationship between the two variables under consideration.

Table 1 shows the characteristics of the HRV.

HRV	Units	Description
<i>Time</i>		
mRR	ms	Mean of RR intervals
SDRR	ms	The standard deviation of RR intervals
mHR	BPM	Mean of heart rate
SDHR	BPM	The standard deviation of heart rate
CVRR		Coefficient variation of RRI
RMSSD	ms	Root mean square of the

		successive differences
pRR20	%	The ratio of the difference in consecutive RRIs over 20 ms
pRR50	%	The ratio of the difference in consecutive RRIs over 50 ms
<i>Frequency</i>		
ULF	ms ²	Power of ultra-low frequency band (0 – 0.003 Hz)
VLF	ms ²	Power of very-low-frequency band (0.003 – 0.04 Hz)
LF	ms ²	Power of low-frequency band (0.04 – 0.15 Hz)
HF	ms ²	Power of high-frequency band (0.15 – 0.4 Hz)
LF/HF		The ratio of LF and HF band powers total

3. RESULTS

The training data for the stress level classification is derived from eight HRV time domain features and four HRV frequency domain features. In the time domain, the eight HRV features used are mRR, SDRR, mHR, SDHR, CVRR, RMSSD, pRR20, and pRR50. In the frequency domain, the four HRV features used are ULF, VLF, LF, and HF. The time obtained at a specific value of accuracy and

reaction time was used as training data for the reference grouping of HRV features, and the result will be the input for the four classification models.

The neural network classification model that was used has 1000 epochs and ten hidden layer parameters. We will get five outputs from the input of eight HRV features in the time domain or four HRV features in the frequency domain, which are classes or labels given in the training data. Resilient backpropagation is used in the neural network classification model that employs optimizer. During the training process, the mean squared error (MSE) method is used to measure error.

The confusion matrix in depicts the results of the neural network classification model training. The output class is a class of data identification results, whereas the target class is the actual class of data.

The training data in the time domain shows that the neural networks classification model has an accuracy rate of 74.2 percent based on the confusion matrix. The correct classification values are found in the fifth class or rest conditions, which account for 65.3 percent of the total.

While the fourth class has the lowest value or the highest stress level, it is 1.1 percent. In the frequency domain, however, data in the second, third, and fourth classes cannot be classified with the correct value.

4. CONCLUSION

The PPG heart rate sensing on a mobile device was verified to work accurately and to provide the functionality required in this study. In moderate motion artefacts, detrending, filtering, and peak detection algorithms from PPG signals, as well as calculation of heart rate variability features in the time and frequency domains, have been shown to work adequately. In machine learning, the value of the answer n-back task is used as a label in training and testing data. When implemented in the time domain, ultra-short-term HRV analysis on 41 participants yielded promising results. In contrast, the frequency domain analysis was still limited to distinguishing between participants performing n-back tasks and those resting.

This occurs because the time used is relatively short, which is the lower limit for frequency domain analysis. When compared to four other algorithms used in the time or frequency domain, the k-nearest neighbour algorithm is the most appropriate for use in this study's classification.

In the time domain, the neural network algorithm is also quite feasible, whereas the discriminant analysis algorithm is quite feasible in the frequency domain. The ability to measure mental stress in a reliable and valid manner will allow many areas of cognitive psychology to be explored further. Future work will include increasing the number of participants, involving

medical or psychological experts to clarify the outcome of the work, and predicting the occurrence of stress.

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